

Efficient Solutions for Quantum Secure Communications in Future Optical Networks

Michela Svaluto Moreolo, *Senior Member, IEEE*, Masab Iqbal, Laia Nadal, *Senior Member, IEEE*,
Raul Muñoz, *Senior Member, IEEE*

*Centre Tecnològic de Telecomunicacions de Catalunya (CTTC/CERCA), Av. Carl Friedrich Gauss, 7,
08860 - Castelldefels (Barcelona) - Spain
e-mail: michela.svaluto@cttc.es*

ABSTRACT

To face the quantum era and the prospect or threat of quantum computing, especially in a disaggregated network environment, the design and implementation of efficient quantum secure communication systems facilitating their integration in the optical network infrastructure is crucial. Quantum key distribution (QKD) is one of the most promising technologies to ensure long-term security. In particular, continuous-variable QKD results as an efficient solution more compatible and suitable to be integrated with conventional optical systems. In this work, quantum secure systems based on QKD for enabling a smooth and sustainable integration in optical networks are introduced, considering the related challenges, towards future secure 6G networks.

Keywords: Quantum key distribution (QKD), optical networks, secure communications.

1. INTRODUCTION

In preparation for the radical technological advances envisioned for future 6G networks, hyperconnectivity, environmental and societal sustainability, reliability and security are important requirements to be addressed. Trusted networks with a high degree of reliability and security are required, and security arises as a crucial aspect, especially when considering open and disaggregated networks.

Telecom operators promote disaggregating the optical networks as a strategy for achieving cost-effective and vendor-neutral open solutions [1]. An evolutionary path is envisioned towards a full disaggregated paradigm, that targets the adoption of white boxes, decoupling the hardware and software (from different providers) using open interfaces, and the use of commercial off-the-shelf (COTS) open components. This strategy drives the deployment of future 6G networks in a more competitive and sustainable way, less dependent on providers and aggregated/closed systems. Also, this provides a unique opportunity for operators to enable programmability and flexibility of open and disaggregated technologies towards supporting future connectivity, but also for directly managing the network security.

The investigation of state of the art and future directions of quantum communications, identifying technologies and challenges, is of paramount importance for enabling future connectivity to face the quantum era, towards a smooth integration with classical networks in view of secure 6G and the quantum Internet [2]. Quantum key distribution (QKD) is one of the most promising technologies to ensure long-term security of optical networks and its implementation with suitable photonic technologies compatible with optical systems facilitates its adoption and integration in optical networks. In particular, continuous-variable QKD (CV-QKD), adopting optical coherent technologies, results more compatible with optical communication technologies and suitable to be integrated with conventional optical systems [3]. Furthermore, the possibility of implementing CV-QKD with COTS components and using photonic integrated circuit (PIC) technology allow providing low cost and low energy consumption solutions, towards a sustainable development of quantum secure communications [4], [5]. Thus, it is of special interest to design efficient QKD schemes/systems, towards an actual implementation and integration in future optical networks. In particular, the coexistence with classical channels/systems should be carefully considered, as well as the adaptability and programmability in view of integrating the proposed QKD-based systems in the network infrastructure, particularly considering a disaggregated environment. Software defined networking (SDN) facilitates this integration and enable a faster adoption of QKD technology and the related services [6], in support of secure 6G networks.

2. QUANTUM KEY DISTRIBUTION IN OPTICAL NETWORKS

QKD ensures long-term security of optical networks, thanks to the fundamental principles of quantum mechanics. It is a method for generating a secret key between two parties, Alice and Bob, based on transmitting quantum states.

There are two main QKD schemes: the discrete variable (DV)-QKD and the continuous variable (CV)-QKD [3]. In the former, single photon detectors (SPD) are required; while, in the latter, optical coherent technologies, based on either homodyne or heterodyne detection, are adopted, making this approach easier to be implemented and more suitable to be integrated in optical networks. Performance in terms of reach and secure key rate

depends on the adopted scheme. DV-QKD is more tolerant to channel losses, achieving longer reach compared to CV-QKD, while CV-QKD outperforms DV-QKD in terms of secure key rate [7], [8].

Alternative protocols and schemes have been proposed for DV- and CV-QKD [3]. In the case of CV-QKD protocols, the encoding is performed by exploiting the in-phase and quadrature components of the electromagnetic field, adopting either Gaussian or discrete modulation at the Alice's transmitter. In Gaussian modulation (GM), the quadrature components of the coherent states prepared by Alice are modulated according to a zero-centred Gaussian distribution. Different discrete modulation (DM) protocols can be applied; they can outperform GM and be more easily implemented adopting optical communication technologies [3].

At Bob's receiver (Rx), either homodyne or heterodyne (shot noise limited) detection can be adopted. In the former case, only one quadrature component is measured at a time; in the latter, both quadrature components are simultaneously measured, doubling the mutual information at the expense of additional 3-dB loss [3]. In the simple schematic of Fig. 1, alternative options for the CV-QKD system are indicated.

A typical CV-QKD implementation is based on the GG02 protocol, proposed by Grosshans and Grangier in 2002 [9]. It adopts Gaussian modulation and homodyne detection.

Unlike early implementations of CV-QKD, true local oscillator (generated locally at Bob's Rx) is required to be adopted in actual implementations, to avoid security breach due to possible accessibility/manipulations by an eavesdropper [10].

In QKD protocols, after states distribution and measurement, in addition to the parameter estimation, further post-processing steps should be performed, including information reconciliation (usually adopting reverse reconciliation, where error correction is performed by Alice based on Bob's information) and privacy amplification, requiring suitable computational algorithms [10]. In CV-QKD, security proof is required, considering eavesdropping attacks (e.g., the collective attack) and DM protocols are characterized by higher reconciliation efficiency than GM [3].

A coherent optical communication system operating in the quantum noise limit can be adopted for CV-QKD. Thus, an implementation with COTS components is possible, as demonstrated in [4]. This also facilitates the adoption of PIC, resulting therefore in a low cost and low energy consumption implementation towards a sustainable quantum network system development [11], [5]. Thus, it is particularly attractive to consider CV-QKD as a suitable option to achieve secure communications and facilitate the integration with optical networks.

In the framework of the Spanish 6G-OPENSEC-KEYS project, we propose to adopt flexible and efficient solutions based on CV-QKD for strengthening the security of 6G networks. Special attention is devoted to designs and implementations that are sustainable in terms of cost and resource usage. To this extent, thanks to the adoption of CV-QKD, easy integration of the proposed technology in optical networks is promoted.

Figure 1. Scenario of coexistence of classical channels generated by a set of BVTs and the quantum channel generated by a QKD system composed of a Tx (Alice) and Rx (Bob). In the insets, possible options for the CV-QKD Tx and Rx are indicated. The coexistence in the spectral and/or spatial (WDM/SDM) domains and the integration of QKD technology in the network infrastructure are facilitated by the adoption of an SDN controller.

2.1 Coexistence with classical channels

The integration of quantum technologies in the current network infrastructure is key to enable a sustainable and smooth transition towards next-generation optical networks and to ensure an optimal resource usage in 6G networks. Therefore, the study and analysis of the coexistence of QKD and conventional channels within optical networks is of paramount relevance, towards identifying optimal solutions to accommodate high-capacity channels, generated by conventional optical transmission systems in beyond 5G and 6G networks, and enabling quantum-safe secure communications.

QKD protocols coexisting with classical channels have been the focus of numerous experiments and demonstrations in recent years, due to the challenging issue of co-propagating a signal at the quantum level with conventional amplified signals in the same transmission medium. The use of alternative bands or a suitable allocation within the C-band adopting wavelength division multiplexing (WDM) can be considered for co-propagating the quantum and the classical channels in a single mode fiber (SMF). For example, DV-QKD systems in the O-band have been integrated with 100 Gb/s classical dense WDM channels in the C-band [12]. The inherent advantages of adopting specialty optical fibers, such as multicore fibers (MCF) or hollow-core fibers, can also be exploited for the coexistence of classical and QKD channels, achieving improved performance. Particularly, it has been demonstrated that space division multiplexing (SDM) adopting MCF enables transmitting multi-Tb/s classical channels in coexistence with the QKD channel [13]. Furthermore, MCF can also be used to improve the secure key rate by parallelizing CV-QKD over multiple cores, as proposed in [14]. The adoption of hollow-core fibers, for co-propagating classical and quantum channels, allows enabling higher launching powers for the classical channels [15].

As indicated in Fig. 1, multiple classical channels can be generated by a set of bandwidth/bitrate variable transceivers (BVTs). Also, a sliceable-BVT (S-BVT) can be considered, where the multiple flows/slices can be eventually aggregated by a multiframe aggregator [16]-[18]. Actually, the use of modular, flexible, high-capacity and programmable transceiver solutions is crucial to address the hyperconnectivity envisioned in 6G networks and the S-BVT is a key element of the envisioned open and disaggregated networks [16], [18]. The multiple channels/flows can be co-propagated with the quantum channel in the same standard SMF (SSMF), adopting WDM technology, and/or considering SDM, adopting either a bundle of fibers or a MCF. Indeed, the channel spacing and the appropriate power to guarantee coexistence and preserving the quantum channel, should be carefully analysed and selected, as well as the impairments (e.g., non-linear effects, such as the Raman scattering) that can affect the transmission should be appropriately considered.

3. SDN AND QKD

Due to the limited reach achievable by the quantum signal [8], in addition to satellite connections, the use of trusted nodes allows to extend the covered distance and also enables QKD networks, connecting nodes and performing key hopping. Accordingly, the keys generated at a starting node are securely transferred from node to node until the end node.

Major efforts have been devoted to point-to-point systems and schemes, while next steps and efforts are required towards achieving reliable quantum networks. To address the multiple challenges posed to achieve this goal, complex aspects must be investigated, where also the key management and control system are involved. SDN can ease the integration of QKD and the key management in the network infrastructure and facilitate the coexistence with conventional systems, enabling quantum secure communications [6] [19]. Thus, it is particularly relevant a synergy of all these technologies, as well as to define and enable key advanced functionalities, as programmability and adaptability, properly designing the quantum secure system elements. This is especially crucial in open and disaggregated environment, promoted by telecom operators for interoperability and for an efficient use of the available network resources and infrastructure. Open and standard application programming interfaces (APIs) are required to export the programmability to the operator's vendor-neutral SDN controller. At the same time, SDN brings security challenges to be addressed, that can be mitigated thanks to the use of QKD. Open test facilities supported by user-friendly interfaces and open access policy can provide QKD use-case validation and user experience for quantum technologies [20].

Considerable efforts towards these goals have been devoted at the Spanish level in the framework of the Madrid Quantum Communication Infrastructure (MadQCI), demonstrating the integration of the QKD technology into real production networks [21].

In the framework of the 6G-OPENSEC-KEYS project, we propose to adopt flexible and efficient solutions based on CV-QKD that can be controllable by software, facilitating the adaptability and interoperability, particularly in a disaggregated and multi-provider environment. The adaptable parameters (such as the operating wavelength, channel power and others depending on the specific adopted technologies) and the programmable elements should be identified and suitably enabled, to optimize the coexistence in different network scenarios and for different use cases. The SDN controller (by means of suitable interfaces) can control the QKD system and also interact with the conventional system, to facilitate the integration of QKD technology in the network infrastructure, considering spectral and spatial channels, as shown in Fig.1.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Secure and robust optical networks are key for future interconnected societies. Quantum technologies will play a major role in this context as they offer inherent security, which also ensures robustness against future security attacks based on quantum computers. For ensuring long-term security, different QKD protocols and implementations can be considered. CV-QKD represents a very attractive candidate to be integrated in the network infrastructure in coexistence with optical systems, thanks to the possibility of being implemented with COTS components and PICs. We propose the adoption of efficient, in terms of cost and resources, and flexible CV-QKD systems, controllable by software, that can facilitate the coexistence with conventional systems, considering the network infrastructure, and an optimal resource usage. An interesting use case is the coexistence with classical channels generated by programmable, flexible and sliceable transceivers. The synergy of SDN, photonic and quantum technologies is envisioned, for addressing the challenges of 6G networks in terms of hyperconnectivity, security and sustainability.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Work funded by the Spanish 6G-OPENSEC-KEYS (TSI-063000-2021-61) and RELAMPAGO (PID2021-127916OB-I00) projects.

REFERENCES

- [1] E. Riccardi, P. Gunning, Ó. G. de Dios, M. Quagliotti, V. López and A. Lord, "An Operator view on the Introduction of White Boxes into Optical Networks," *J. Lightwave Technol.*, vol. 36, no. 15, pp. 3062-3072, Aug. 2018.
- [2] A. Lord, C. White, and E. H. Salas, "Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) and the Quantum Internet: The challenges facing this new technology," in *Proc. OFC 2021*, Th2A.1.
- [3] I. B. Djordjevic, *Physical-Layer Security and Quantum Key Distribution*, Springer, Cham, Switzerland (2019).
- [4] M. Rückmann, C. G. Schaeffer, "CV-QKD System Using a Commercial Coherent Transceiver Module," in *Proc. OFC 2021*, paper F4E.2.
- [5] J. Aldama, et al., "InP-based CV-QKD PIC Transmitter," in *Proc. OFC 2023*, paper M1I.3.
- [6] A. Aguado, et al., "Enabling Quantum Key Distribution Networks via Software-Defined Networking," *Proc. ONDM*, 2020.
- [7] A. Boaron, et al., "Secure quantum key distribution over 421 km of optical fiber," *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, 121(19), 190502, 2018.
- [8] Y. Zhang, et al., "Long-distance continuous-variable quantum key distribution over 202.81 km of fiber," *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, 125(1), 010502, 2020.
- [9] F. Grosshans, P. Grangier, "Continuous variable quantum cryptography using coherent states," *Phys Rev Lett* 88, 057902, 2002.
- [10] E. Diamanti, A. Leverrier, "Distributing Secret Keys with Quantum Continuous Variables: Principle, Security and Implementations," *Entropy*, vol. 17, pp. 6072-6092, 2015.
- [11] "Quantum PIC position paper," April 2022, https://www.photonics21.org/news/Verlinkungen/2022/QPIC_position_paper_26-4-22_final.pdf
- [12] A. Wonfor et al., "Field trial of multi-node, coherent-one-way quantum key distribution with encrypted 5×100G DWDM transmission system," in *Proc. ECOC 2019*.
- [13] E. Hugues-Salas et al., "11.2 Tb/s Classical Channel Coexistence With DV-QKD Over a 7-Core Multicore Fiber," in *J. Lightwave Technol.*, vol. 38, no. 18, pp. 5064-5070, 15 Sept.15, 2020.
- [14] S. Sarmiento et al., "Continuous-variable quantum key distribution over a 15 km multi-core fiber," *New J. Phys.*, vol. 24, 063011, 2022.
- [15] O. Alia et al., "DV-QKD Coexistence With 1.6 Tbps Classical Channels Over Hollow Core Fibre," *J. Lightwave Technol.*, vol. 40, no. 16, pp. 5522-5529, Aug. 2022
- [16] M. Svaluto Moreolo, J. M. Fabrega, L. Nadal, R. Martínez, R. Casellas, "Synergy of Photonic Technologies and Software-Defined Networking in the Hyperconnectivity Era," *J. Lightwave Technol.*, Vol. 37, No. 16, pp. 3902-3910, May 2019.
- [17] M. Svaluto Moreolo, et al., "Programmable VCSEL-based photonic system architecture for future agile Tb/s metro networks," *J. Opt. Commun. Netw.*, Vol. 13, No. 2, pp. A187-A199, Feb. 2021.
- [18] L. Nadal, et al., "Programmable disaggregated multi-dimensional S-BVT as an enabler for high capacity optical metro networks," *J. Opt. Commun. Netw.*, Vol. 13, No. 6, pp. C31-C40, June 2021.
- [19] A. Gatto, et al., "Quantum Technologies for future Quantum Optical Networks," in *Proc. ONDM 2021*.
- [20] <https://openqkd.eu/>
- [21] D. Lopez, J. P. Brito, A. Pastor, V. Martin, C. Sánchez, D. Rincon, and V. Lopez, "Madrid Quantum Communication Infrastructure: a testbed for assessing QKD technologies into real production networks," in *Proc. OFC 2021*, paper Th2A.